

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: SPAIN

3edata

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3edata is a Small and Medium Sized Enterprise (SME) founded in 2016, as a spin-off from the [University of Santiago de Compostela](#) (Spain). This corporate project was initiated by 3 researchers from the Campus Terra - USC, aiming to put their knowledge and experience, acquired within the University, at the service of the public and private sector; and to do it from a different and more focused and practical perspective.

private. Our goal is to improve their capacity to optimize available resources while minimizing environmental costs and to contribute to the sustainability of our planet. To achieve this goal, we apply our knowledge to the development of new automatic tools for assessing, evaluating and monitoring natural resources using EO technologies (remote sensing and *in situ* data gathering) in the fields of forestry, agriculture, environment and water quality.

WHAT DO WE DO

In the field of water quality and management, our background comes not only from the EO domain, but also from Ecology and Limnological Sciences. Furthermore, we are members of European and global networks working with High Frequency Water Quality Data (HFWQD) and modelling, such as GLEON.

Since 2016 3edata is developing different multiplatform tools to monitor status and changes in forest stands, crop fields and waterbodies. We apply our expertise in Optical Remote Sensing, EO data processing, automatic classification, LiDAR, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) technology and *in situ* sensors to provide innovative solutions for the spatially explicit retrieval and interpretation of environmental data for

Fig. 1 Detail of UAV flight and image composition (upper left and right) and chl-a maps of two drinking water reservoirs obtained with different sensors: Sentinel 2 MSI (lower left) and a multispectral camera on board UAV (lower right).

The combination of expertise in data management, Remote Sensing (RS), GIS technologies, Forestry and Environmental Sciences (including Limnology) are the backbone of 3edata and the basis for our main job: the development of monitoring and assessment tools for the management of natural resources through the work of Data Analysts and Engineers.

In 2018 3edata was recognized by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities as an "Innovative SME" due to our work in Research, Development and Innovation with competitive actions and projects in cooperation with Public Research Centers within the framework of Regional, National and European funding institutions.

MISSION AND VISION

Our aim is to promote the synoptic view that Earth Observation (EO) technologies can deliver into the hands of natural resources managers. These technologies and the downstream data they generate, when presented in an intuitive and comprehensive way, provide support to the decision-making process of our clients, both public and

managers. 3edata is also involved in public procurement contracts for innovative technology and currently developing new solutions based on EO Technologies to cover the specific needs of the Public Administration in different sectors.

In the field of Limnology, 3edata is developing multiplatform monitoring tools for small to medium-sized water bodies especially focusing its efforts in addressing problems of high social impacts like eutrophication, Harmful Algal Blooms and turbidity in drinking water reservoirs. We use multispectral satellite imagery analysis, data intensive *in situ* monitoring technologies and UAV multispectral and hyperspectral data gathering to develop algorithms for the synoptic and spatially explicit quantification of chl-a and turbidity. The combination of observational platforms acquiring HFWQD both in time (profiling autonomous devices) and space (Autonomous Underwater Vehicles) with RS technologies, have been the focus of our latest 3edata research projects in collaboration with the EMALCSA Chair, the University of Santiago de Compostela and the University of A Coruña.

Research and development activities are a central part of 3edata's philosophy of constant improvement. An example of the activities carried out with this objective was the participation of our researchers in a project within the framework of the "Transnational Access 2019" call of the EU AQUACOSM Network. In the HiREMOT project, developed within the summer 2019 [IGB-Lakelab](#) CONNECT Project experiment, researchers from CSIRO Australia, the City University of New York and 3edata carried out research focused on high-resolution remote sensing of optical and temperature lake characteristics.

Recent Publications

Cillero C, Domínguez JA, Delgado J, Hinojo BA, Cereijo JL, Cheda FA, Díaz-Varela RA. 2020. An UAV and satellite multispectral data approach to monitor water quality in small reservoirs. *Remote Sensing* 12: 1514.

Mantzouki E, *et al.* (included C. Cillero). 2018. Temperature effects explain continental scale distribution of cyanobacterial toxins. *Toxins* 10: 156.

Díaz Varela RA, Calvo Iglesias MS, Cillero Castro C, Díaz Varela ER. 2018. Sub-metric analysis of vegetation structure in bog-heathland mosaics using very high resolution RPAS imagery. *Ecological Indicators* 89: 861-873.

Mantzouki E, *et al.* (included C. Cillero). 2018. Data descriptor: A European multi lake survey dataset of environmental variables, phytoplankton pigments and cyanotoxins. *Scientific Data*. DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2018.226.

Cillero Castro C, Díaz Varela RA, Rubinos Román MA, Ramil Rego P. 2016. Assessment of anthropogenic pressures on South European Atlantic bogs (NW Spain) based on hydrochemical data. *Hydrobiologia* 774: 137-154.

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